

EXPLORERS

Exceed your limits.
Become the BEST.

Dew Mobility

 dewmobility.com

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Dew Mobility is a California State corporation with partners like Microsoft, Samsung, Nokia, Orange, Sensoplex and Vuzix- with 4 business units: Internet of Things, AI, Machine Learning and cyber security applications.

TheLed by a team of leaders from various Fortune companies, Dew is poised to meet the demands of a rapidly growing industry. Our experienced development team designs and creates applications for all major platforms.

OUR PARTNERS

READY FOR:

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

OPEN IDEAS

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Health
Smart City

